

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF FORMING CREATIVE SKILLS BASED ON CREATIVE APPROACHES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the classification and methods used in the process of forming creative skills based on creative approaches in native language classes of elementary school.

INTRODUCTION

All over the world, scientific research is being carried out aimed at forming children as individuals from an early age, educating their abilities and aesthetic feelings, increasing their intellectual skills, and helping them realize their creative abilities. In his scientific research, the activity of interests, creative illumination, interest in inventiveness, critical and logical thoughts on events and given texts, and creative possibilities are determined in children of junior school age.

Non-standard forms of lessons and interactive teaching methods are important in developing the creative skills of elementary school students based on creative approaches, attracting students' attention. "Interactive" is derived from the English word "interactive" and means "inter"- "mutual", "act"- "movement, activity". [3] Creativity of elementary school students

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Sh. Abdullayeva, one of the scientists of our republic. M. Kulakhmetova, Ch. T. Shakirova's work on organizing lessons in primary classes on the basis of modular innovative technologies and forming students' creative thinking skills can be acknowledged.

Also, various aspects of teaching in elementary schools of general secondary schools were studied by B. R. Adizov, R. Ibragimova, Sh. Nurullayeva, Sh. Sharipov, F. Khojjiyeva. The psychological foundations of the thinking process were studied by E. Ghaziyev, V. Karimova, R. Sunnatova and Z. Nishonova, while the problem of developing sanogenic (healthy) thinking was studied by M. Ismailov.

In the general secondary education system, the influence of students' thinking, creative organization of the learning process, problem-based research method, creative works, didactic games on the learning and thinking of students secret has been the object of research of many

scientists. For example, the process of teaching students to think creatively in the process of literary education is reflected in the research of Q. Husanboyeva.[4]

The researcher says that positive results can be achieved in teaching students to think creatively if the following are followed during primary education:

- 1) if the necessary conditions for students' creative thinking are created during the lessons;
- 2) if didactic games and tasks that teach students to think creatively are consistently used in class;
- 3) if creative work methods are consistently and regularly used in the educational process;
- 4) problem situations are created during the lesson and students' participation in them is ensured;
- 5) if the teacher himself has mastered the skills of creative thinking;
- 6) if the teacher-student cooperation is established correctly, the set goal can be achieved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The interactive method, as a type of method widely used today, is the main method aimed at forming the ability of students to think independently, increasing the level of critical and analytical thinking.[3] Forming and developing creative actions and skills of students, demonstrating the ability to work together in small and large groups, exchanging ideas with each other, creative approach to various situations is an important necessity today. The age and level of knowledge of the members of each group is taken into account. In this process, the ability to apply pedagogical creative ideas in practice also requires pedagogical skills and skills from the teacher. Special emphasis should be placed on innovative ideas in problematic situations. This, in turn, is directly related to the pedagogical experience and qualifications of the teacher. Because the use of interactive methods requires a real creative approach. In any situation, which method or methods are used, students' intellectual and practical activity increases, their interest increases, and their worldview expands.

Currently, practical and innovative games are effectively used in the educational process. These practical-innovative games serve to enable the teacher to work effectively, to create the

necessary conditions for students to independently master educational materials, both individually and together with the teacher.

In the class environment, organizing games among students within the framework of the topic, organizing groups, assigning certain tasks and assignments to each group member taking into account the imbalances in the scope of knowledge, making general conclusions about the assignment, analyzing achievements and shortcomings serving to increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

Practical games - games that provide an opportunity to simulate the organization of certain practical actions. Game technologies (game education) - all forms of mastering social experiences: knowledge, skills, competence and the process of creative thinking. aimed at creating.

Blended learning is a relatively new, but increasingly popular, form of modern education.

Blended learning is a form of learning based on online learning materials and group learning under the guidance of a teacher. and teacher support. Due to the use of –blended learning|| (mixed teaching) during group sessions, each student communicates, demonstrating the positive changes that are occurring in him in mastering the educational materials. learns skills, repeats previous material and prepares to learn a new topic. Blended learning often relies on tasks and is organized on the basis of basic, important information, and additional materials are delivered to the student through an online platform. The success of blended learning is determined by the correct selection of educational tools. The advantage of this form of education is that the student himself determines the speed of learning the learning material and the intensity of the educational process. [7]

The role of mother tongue science in the formation of creative skills of primary school students based on creative approaches is incomparable. The mother tongue is a subject that not only teaches lexical and grammatical norms, but also serves to develop the potential of students to listen and understand, read correctly, and apply orthographic and orthographic norms. For the logical, critical, creative thinking of the student, special attention is paid to reading comprehension in mother tongue classes.

A student who mastered his mother tongue satisfactorily learns other subjects. A student with perfect reading literacy can think logically, critically, and creatively by reading the texts studied in other subjects, and the ability to apply the knowledge gained in life is developed. Also, one of the main tasks for the teacher is to adapt the practical tasks designed to work with texts that meet the requirements of the international assessment program (PISA, PIRLS) aimed at forming the student's logical thinking and practical skills. It is intended to form the skills of understanding the text, analytical, critical thinking and reaction. [2]

Development of speech (communicative) competence aimed at thinking, understanding the opinion of others, expressing one's own opinion in oral and written form in accordance with speech conditions correctly and fluently; develops the learner's practical knowledge of language construction (phonetics (orphoepy), lexicon, word composition, morphology, syntax, writing and spelling, punctuation, speech styles, stylistic concepts).

In mother tongue classes, students are focused on developing their creative skills based on creative approaches:

- ☒ To give students a grammatical task about creative thinking;
- ☒ Studying their results, reviewing their creative works;
- ☒ To determine the topics of interest of the students and conduct a conversation on this topic;
- ☒ Creating the necessary conditions that allow them to be creative in expressing their thoughts; (interview can be individual or group);
- ☒ Creating problem situations that encourage students to think creatively during the lesson and taking into account every opinion expressed by students;
- ☒ To study students' creative writing. Creative works of students: essays, written works, drawings on free topics, etc. are important tools in this;
- ☒ In class and extracurricular activities, various interesting didactic games and traditional methods are used to encourage students to think creatively, to involve all students in the class.[5]

Forms, methods and methods of organizing the joint activities of the teacher and the student in teaching the mother tongue are developing and being updated in connection with the improvement of the educational system. As native teaching methods, explanatory statement method, interview method, analysis-synthesis method, independent work method, inductive and deductive methods are used in the organization of native language education classes.

Narrative method was one of the main methods used in mother tongue classes. In this case, the teacher has determined the students' knowledge of the topic being studied before the presentation. This encouraged the students to follow and listen to the teacher's explanation and to be active. Based on the nature of the grammatical topic in the teacher's statement, i.e., the method of presentation, the teacher presented the information in his own words. In this case, the teacher is charged with the task of clearly, succinctly and coherently explaining the important points of the studied grammatical topic with the analysis of examples. The presentation method in primary classes is designed for 3-5 minutes, depending on the age and state of memory of the students.

The conversational method is widely used in the teaching of the mother tongue in primary grades and is considered a method suitable for the nature of students of this stage. The interview method is also known as the question-and-answer method. The interview method asks the teacher to find the educational material that reflects the nature of the topic, to identify the important features of the grammatical topic, to distinguish their similar and different aspects, to group according to their similar and different aspects, to generalize, to draw conclusions. It requires to make and give them consistently to the students.

The use of the interview method as a problem-based teaching method in primary classes has a great effect on the activation of students in education. The problem-based teaching method was founded by the American pedagogue and psychologist Dune in 1894. The purpose of this method is not only to help mastering scientific concepts, but also to develop students' cognitive abilities and creative abilities. During the conversation, a problem is put before the student by the teacher's task and a problematic situation is created in the lesson. The student solves this problem based on his previous knowledge. Due to the lack of life experience of elementary school students, the teacher asks questions that help to solve the problem. If the student cannot solve the problem, the teacher has to solve it. Therefore, the method of problem-

based teaching in the primary class is also called the semi-research problem-based method. For example, the problem-based teaching method can be used to organize lexical-semantic and grammatical exercises. This method can be used from 1st grade.

In elementary school mother tongue classes, the independent work method is mainly used in the process of exercises in the part of strengthening the learned topic. Pupils perform independent tasks orally or in writing on the teacher's assignment. The task should not be difficult and time-consuming, it should be completed within a certain time, so that the students' strength is sufficient. The task for independent work is given from the 1st grade and it gradually becomes more complicated. From the 1st grade, "Check the words you wrote in the dictionary", "Write the names of vegetables in alphabetical order according to the picture", "Watch the picture". Identify the things depicted in it and write their names. The analysis-synthesis method entered literacy classes through the activities of Rustuzem schools and Tatar teachers.

Analysis is applied to the process of mother tongue education in order to identify the important features of the grammatical phenomenon, to reveal and strengthen new aspects of the learned grammatical concept.

Phonetic, lexical, morphological and syntactic analysis is the practical manifestation of this method. Synthesis is the improvement of grammatical material studied in parts. For example, when studying word groups such as nouns, adjectives, verbs, numbers, words related to them are given, and they make sentences with their participation, make sentences from mixed words, compose a text by arranging mixed sentences based on the development of events, The method of synthesis is shown in works such as creating a story based on the analyzed picture.

In the analysis-synthesis method, student activation depends on the teacher's questions and assignments to students, and the forms of work organization. In the induction method, students observe, analyze, and draw conclusions and definitions based on the language evidence recommended by the teacher. In the method of deduction, the student gets acquainted with a ready-made rule - a definition and discovers its essence based on linguistic evidence. The effectiveness of these methods depends on the content of the teacher's questions and tasks being focused on the important aspects of the grammatical phenomenon, consistency, forms of activity organization, educational tools (textbook, dictionaries of various types, pictures, tables, technical tools). . [6]

Debate lesson. In this method, students are given a topic one day in advance. Students read the topic, find answers to the questions, and the answers to those questions are discussed in groups. Or a problem is written on the class board, and if it has several solutions, it is worked on in the form of a debate. In this, students' activity increases and they behave freely.

The highest expression of creative thinking and independent thinking is text creation.

The ability to express an idea in written form (a text expressing a complete idea) is a complex process, and the purpose of mother tongue education is embodied in this parameter. The skills and competences acquired by the student in the process of learning his mother tongue are reflected in the text he creates. When the student creates a written text, the level of the following skills is determined:

a) that the thought is expressed in logical consistency;

b) thinking, level of complexity of the subject (simple, complex, abstract-concrete, abstract, etc.);

d) relevance of the description to the topic and substantive value;

e) level of appropriate use of language means of expression in the description;

g) the level of creative thinking is determined;

f) quality of spelling (written) literacy.

✓ Writing a fairy tale, a story. It is known that students know a lot of fairy tales, but they find it difficult to create a fairy tale themselves. This creative-practical type of work expands the imagination of students, develops their oral and written speech, learns to think creatively, and introduces them to the world of strange events. Teaching students to create a fairy tale begins with introducing them to the specific features of this genre. Children should know the knot, development point and solution of the story in the fairy tale, be aware of its language features, have the skills to use figurative tools such as exaggeration, simile, animation, reduction in their place. The beginning part, such as continuing the given fairy tales, creating a fairy tale based on the given pictures, filling in the spaces left by the speech of the heroes, improves the text creation skills of the students, helps them to search creatively, develop their thinking, and develop their fantasy.

✓ In the process of teaching the mother tongue, the statement has a special place in the expression of thoughts in oral and written forms.

✓ Narrative is one of the types of written work written based on reading or retelling the text, which is intended to develop students' creative thinking. This word is Arabic and means "expressing", "illuminating" and "notifying", and starting from the 2nd grade, students are taught to write a statement. teaches independent, critical thinking. Writing a statement is one of the types of creative work and performs the following tasks:

☑ Formation of the student's ability to explain a certain text;

☑ Teaching the student to analyze;

☑ Strengthening the student's memory;

☑ Compose the content of the student's written speech.

☑ Teaching the student to think creatively

Essay is one of the types of written work in which the student independently and creatively illuminates the subject. According to the pedagogic scientists, the essay is a useful educational tool in the formation of personality, it arouses emotions in the student and directs him to intellectual independence, creative thinking, evaluation of what he has seen and learned. , teaches to find cause-and-effect relationships between events, compare them and draw conclusions. In this sense, the word essay is Arabic and means "to create", "to build" and "to start". The essay is written according to a clear plan, and it performs the following main tasks:

to develop the student's feelings (emotions);

- development of the student's mind (intellect);

- teaching the student to think independently and creatively;

- formation of the student's ability to evaluate incidents and events.

In this sense, by writing an essay, elementary school students develop emotional and mental feelings, and they develop independent, creative, and personal thinking abilities.[2]

Essays and narratives allow students to develop the skills of independent thinking at the required level, and represent the ability of students to think deeply and come to the right conclusions about reality (phenomenon) through creative thinking.

CONCLUSION

The advantages of organizing primary education mother tongue and reading literacy lessons using non-standard lesson formats:

- 1) It leads to good learning of the teaching content;
- 2) Sincere relations are established between the student-teacher and the students; Forms of teaching take place in different forms during the educational process (individual, pair, group, large groups);
- 3) The educational process becomes highly motivated by satisfying educational needs; Educational material is better remembered by giving, receiving and processing information.
- 4) The skills of communicating, expressing opinions, and exchanging opinions are formed. During the learning process, the student's self-evaluation, self-control, and critical view develop.
- 5) The lesson becomes interesting for the student. A creative approach to the study process, a positive attitude is manifested.
- 6) Each student leads to independent thinking, research and observation. Also, the teacher is required to follow didactic rules when using non-standard lesson forms.

The use of these creative methods and methods will help primary school students to strive for creativity, creative approach to training, independent, critical thinking, constant critical reflection and self-analysis. Based on the modern dictionaries of psychology and pedagogy, it is possible to describe creative methods of the teacher as the level of knowledge in thoughts, feelings, communication, special activity, creative approach. Correct use of creative methods in native language classes allows students to reproduce existing information and create an unlimited new model of it, because the ability to think broadly within this subject is formed. It is clear from this that the importance of using creative methods in mother tongue lessons makes a worthy contribution to the formation of the young generation in the future as independent, critical, creative thinkers, self-confident individuals who can quickly enter the social society. That's why today the main pedagogical technologies of imperial, cognitive, heuristic, creative, inversion, inclusive methods are widely used in the educational process.

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